

A Matchmaking Module for Real-World MaaS Applications

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Abstract

Nowadays, being able to move around Europe has become an essential need for the European citizens, and several services have arisen to satisfy this need. In this environment, the Mobility-as-a-Service model has emerged aiming to provide several heterogeneous mobility services through a single access point. One of the most important components of a real-world MaaS application is the one that matches the travellers' trip requests with the available mobility services. In this paper, we describe such a module for real-world MaaS applications. In particular, we describe the functionalities and sub-components of the Matchmaking Module used by the real-world MaaS application implemented in the context of the H2020 European research project MyCorridor. Preliminary experimental results indicate that the main functionality of the Matchmaking Module is highly accepted by the end users.

KEYWORDS:

Mobility-as-a-Service, MaaS, Matchmaking Module

Introduction

Over the last few years, an increasing number of people have moved in urban areas as of the better employment opportunities and the living standards they offer. Following this urbanization increase, and combined with the increased need for transportation it creates, the demand for innovative and sustainable mobility solutions is constantly rising. Several technological advancements have led to the digitalization of a vast variety of services, leveraging the vast amount of available information, whereas new business models have transformed the way that these services are provided. In addition, within the emerging paradigm of smart cities, the concept of Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) has developed to a new mobility business model that provides efficient integration of different services, offering on-demand access from a single point.

MaaS Alliance [1], a public-private partnership aiming to enhance the adoption of the MaaS concept throughout Europe, defined MaaS as the integration of various forms of transportation services into a single service accessible on demand. This unified gateway offers the ability to combine different

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transportation modes, including shared mobility options and public transport, providing an interconnected way of booking and paying for the purchased services using a single application.

This innovative combination of mobility services led to a shift towards multimodal smart mobility systems that provide flexible and convenient solutions, allowing the efficient travel across different countries. However, as the amount of available services increases, the successful fulfillment of a traveller's trip requests becomes tightly connected to the efficient combination of the variety of MaaS offerings. Therefore, the selection of services that best suit the travellers' transportation needs is considered a key concept for offering convenient and satisfactory MaaS mobility packages. Towards this direction, this paper describes a module responsible for matching the travellers' trip requests with the different types of services available in a real-world MaaS platform. The proposed module, namely the Matchmaking Module, takes into account the features of the trip request itself, the travellers' preferences, and the characteristics of the mobility services available in the MaaS platform, in order to identify the mobility solutions that meet the requirements of the trip request in the best possible way. The proposed module was implemented in the context of the H2020 European research project MyCorridor.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents some works from the current MaaS literature focusing on various aspects of MaaS. Section 3 describes the two main matchmaking scenarios defined in the context of MyCorridor project, and presents the functionality and the implementation details of the sub-components of the Matchmaking Module. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper by reviewing its main contributions and proposes some future research directions.

Related work

Since its initial introduction as an innovative transportation alternative, MaaS has been the subject of various research efforts. For example, Karlsson et al. [2] presented the findings from the first trial of Ubigo MaaS application in Gothenburg, Sweden. Additionally, Kamargianni et al. [3] presented a comprehensive review of the background and the key points of MaaS systems, and provided an index to evaluate the level of mobility integration for each one. Similarly, Sochor et al. [4] proposed a MaaS topology based on the different types of service integration, and examined the various technical, societal, business and user requirements. Moreover, Jittrapirom et al. [5] provided a critical review of MaaS definitions, schemes, and key challenges, and presented a framework to classify its core characteristics. Furthermore, Li and Voegelé [6] provided a summarization of the required conditions of MaaS operation, and developed a checklist for potential developers to assess whether MaaS can be implemented in a city. Similarly, Goulding and Kamargianni [7] proposed an index for evaluating a city's readiness for MaaS, which was based on several characteristics including data sharing, transport infrastructure and citizen familiarity and willingness.

Considering the emergence of new business models and forms of partnerships among private and public transport operators, Kamargianni and Matyas [8] identified the different actors and their roles

within the MaaS business ecosystem, while Eckhardt et al. [9] presented and analyzed existing business models of MaaS operators that had been addressed within the MAASiFiE project. From a different perspective, Mulley et al. [10] investigated the ways in which public transport can contribute to the development of MaaS, focusing on the provision of mobility solutions that would enhance accessibility for the elderly and people with disabilities. Similarly, Smith et al. [11] described the various development scenarios of MaaS and examined their implications for future public transport, while Hirschhorn et al. [12] examined governance responses to MaaS developments in Amsterdam, Birmingham, and Helsinki. From another point of view, Rantasila [13] explored the impact of MaaS on land use in Finland.

In their alluring work Matyas and Kamargianni [14] conducted a survey in the Greater London area and deduced that users consider that MaaS bundles offer added-value through shared transportation modes. Additionally, the potential uptake of MaaS subscription plans was examined by Ho et al. [15] using a stated choice study. This study indicated that infrequent car users presented the highest likelihood to adopt MaaS offerings in contrast to the ones who used their car frequently. Moreover, a stated preference (SP) experiment was presented by Matyas and Kamargianni [16], aiming to investigate the decision-making process of selecting MaaS plans. Furthermore, Ahtela and Viitamo [17] investigated the factors that affect the choice of daily commuting modes, along with the changes that will enhance the shift from private cars to sustainable alternatives.

Considering that the seamless operation of MaaS platforms is based on the integration of the variety of services, Melis et al. [18] highlighted the potentialities of using the microservices architectural style in the context of MaaS and designed an infrastructure as a marketplace for mobility services. Also, a compelling study, presented by Carvalho et al. [19], examined the opportunities for Edge-Oriented Computing and Machine Learning to enhance MaaS concepts such as trip-planning and effective choice of subscription plans. Finally, from the security perspective, Callegati et al. [20] highlighted the potential risks of malicious users activity within a MaaS ecosystem, and presented an overlay networking architecture that can act as an effective countermeasure.

Matchmaking Module

The Matchmaking Module is responsible for matching the traveller's trip requests with the services registered in the MyCorridor MaaS platform. The module comprises of three sub-components, namely the *Data Receiver*, the *Data Parser* and the *Matchmaker*. In what follows, we present the main matchmaking scenarios defined in the context of the MyCorridor project, along with the functionality of the sub-components of the Matchmaking Module.

Matchmaking scenarios

In the context of MyCorridor project, two main scenarios involve a matchmaking process. The first ad hoc trip-request scenario starts with the traveller requesting a new trip by providing the necessary

information for the trip, i.e., the origin, the destination, the date, the time, and the preferred transportation mode. This information is transferred to MyCorridor's trip-planning module, which generates trips that satisfy the trip requested. After that, the generated trips are transferred to the Matchmaking Module, received by the Data Receiver, parsed by the Data Parser, and the matchmaking process is performed by the Matchmaker. In particular, the Matchmaker taking into account the information of the trip request, the traveller's preferences, and the characteristics of the services registered in the MyCorridor platform, match to each leg of each trip a set of services that satisfy the requirements of the particular leg. This scenario is called *MaaS&Go*.

The second scenario does not involve the participation of the MyCorridor's trip-planning module because it refers to regular travellers that already know the route (or routes) they prefer and just want to buy services for this route. In this scenario, the process starts again with the traveller providing all the necessary information for the trip request. However, this time, the traveller's input is transferred directly to the Matchmaking Module without first passing through the trip-planning module. Then, similarly to the *MaaS&Go* scenario, the input information is received by the Data Receiver and parsed by the Data Parser. Finally, the Matchmaker identifies the services that best satisfy the input requirements based on the traveller's preferences and the characteristics of the services registered in the MyCorridor platform. This scenario is called *MaaS Packs*.

Data Receiver

The first sub-component of the Matchmaking Module is the Data Receiver. It is responsible for communicating with the appropriate modules in order to receive all the necessary data for the matchmaking process, including the trips that are generated by the trip-planning module, the traveller's preferences, and the services registered in the MyCorridor MaaS platform. Within MyCorridor platform, information is exchanged by a RESTful API called MyCorridor MaaS API. Therefore, the Data Receiver essentially implements a RESTful client by wrapping the popular cURL [21] library. The Data Receiver was implemented using the C++ programming language in the QtCreator [22] integrated development environment (IDE), and its source code was documented using Doxygen [23] software reference documentation tool.

Data Parser

The Data Parser is the sub-component of the Matchmaking Module responsible for parsing the data received by the Data Receiver and transforming them into appropriate internal data structures. The structures that were defined to facilitate the overall matchmaking process are described below:

- **Point:** It represents a point in the two-dimensional plane, uniquely identified by its latitude and longitude.
- **BoundingBox:** It represents a rectangle in the two-dimensional plane. It is uniquely identified by its down left and upper right corners, which are represented by two Point objects.
- **LegGeometry:** It represents the underlying geometric representation of a trip's leg, i.e. a polyline. Each object of this data structure contains a variable representing the length of the

corresponding leg and a variable representing the polyline as an array of Point objects.

- **Leg:** It represents a trip's leg. In addition to the LegGeometry object, two Point objects representing the origin and the destination of the leg are included. Variables representing the start time, the end time, the duration, the distance covered and the transportation mode of the trip are also included. The transportation mode of the leg is a value assigned to each trip's leg by the Trip-Planner.
- **Trip:** It represents a trip returned by MyCorridor's trip-planning module. This data structure includes two Point objects representing the origin and the destination of the trip, an array of Leg objects representing its legs, as well as variables representing the date, the start time, the end time, the duration and the distance of the trip.
- **POILocation:** It represents the location of a point of interest (POI). A POI may be a point of cultural interest (e.g., a museum, a library, and an archaeological site), an entertainment spot (e.g., a restaurant, and a bar) or a point of general interest (e.g. an airport, and a bus station). This data structure encapsulates a Point object and contains variables representing the address, the city, and the country of the POI, as well as the distance of the POI from the actual position of the traveller.
- **POI:** It represents a point of interest (POI). This data structure encapsulates a POILocation object, and contains variables representing the name and the category of the POI.
- **Traveller:** It represents a traveller. Specifically, it contains a subset of the attributes of a traveller, including the routing preference of the traveller, a set of preferred transportation modes, variables denoting the preference of the traveller for specific type of services (e.g., mobility, and traffic management services), and a set of preferred POI objects.
- **ServiceLocation:** It represents one operating area (i.e., city or country) of a service. This data structure encapsulates a BoundingBox object, and additionally contains a variable representing the name of the area.
- **ServiceOperationPeriod:** It represents one operation period for a service. This data structure contains variables representing the day of the week, the start time, and the end time of the operation period.
- **Service:** It represents a service registered in the MyCorridor platform. This data structure contains variables representing the name, the internal categorization, the mode, the registration status, and the average rating of the service (calculated based on travellers' feedback). In addition, it contains a set of ServiceLocation objects and a set of ServiceOperationPeriod objects that represent the operating areas and the operation periods of the service, respectively.

All the aforementioned data structures are accompanied with functions that facilitate the matchmaking process. These set of functions are additionally utilized for accessing information (i.e., accessors) in the data structures and for implementing computations. Within MyCorridor, information is exchanged in JSON [24] format. Therefore, the Data Parser implements JSON parsing using the RapidJSON [25] C++ JSON parsing library. The Data Parser was implemented using the C++ programming language in

the QtCreator IDE, and its source code was documented using Doxygen.

Matchmaker

The Matchmaker is the most essential sub-component of the Matchmaking Module as it is responsible for the actual implementation of the matchmaking process. This process initiates provided the required data has been collected by the Data Receiver and parsed by the Data Parser. However, the process presents different characteristics for the MaaS&Go and the MaaSPacks scenarios, respectively.

Regarding the MaaS&Go scenario, the matchmaking process starts with the identification of the optimal trip among those generated by the trip-planning module, based on the traveller's preferences. In particular, the Matchmaker checks the routing preference of the traveller and the corresponding characteristics of the trips. Then, the services of the MyCorridor platform are matched to each leg of each trip returned by the trip-planning module (i.e., both the optimal and the non-optimal) based on the satisfaction of the following set of rules:

1. The registration status of the service should be "Registered". This means that the service has been checked and found compliant with the MyCorridor platform's operating rules.
2. The category of the service should be "Mobility", "Infomobility", "Traffic Management", or "Added Value", provided that the traveller has selected to receive the corresponding type of services (more information about services' categories within MyCorridor can be found in [26]).
3. If a service's category is "Mobility", the mode of the service should match the mode of the leg of the trip. The mode attribute is assigned to a leg of a trip from the trip-planning module, while the mode of the service is manually added to each mobility service from the MaaS operator based on the type of the service.
4. If a service's category is "Infomobility" and its subcategory is "Park&Ride", the service's mode should be "CAR". (more information about services' subcategories within MyCorridor can be found in [26])
5. At least one operating area of the service should cover both the start and the end points of the leg of the trip. This means that both the start and the end points of the leg should fall into the service's operating areas. It is not necessary for the points to fall in the same operating area, because if this was the case, then only city trips could be served and MyCorridor aims to serve both in-border and cross-border trips.
6. At least one operation period of the service should cover both the start and end dates and times of the leg of the trip. This means that both the start and end time of the leg should belong to the same time period, which is one of the time periods of operation of the service, assuming that the trip is continuous.

Regarding the MaaSPacks scenario, the matchmaking process initiates with the identification of the services that satisfy the traveller's trip request requirements, as the trip planning process is not

involved. The matching of a specific service to the traveller's trip request is based on the following rules:

1. The registration status of the service should be "Registered". This means that the service has been checked and found compliant with the MyCorridor platform's operating rules.
2. The category of the service should be "Mobility", "Infomobility", "Traffic Management", or "Added Value", provided that the traveller has selected to receive the corresponding type of services.
3. If the service's cluster is "Mobility", the mode of the service should belong to the set of preferred transportation modes of the traveller. The preferred transportation modes are selected by the traveller during the profile configuration process, while the mode of the service is manually added to each mobility service from the MaaS aggregator based on the type of the service
4. The mobility product of the service should belong to the set of mobility products selected by the traveller (more information about mobility products within MyCorridor can be found in [26]).
5. At least one operating area of the service should cover both the origin and the destination of the traveller's trip request. This means that both the origin and the destination points should fall in service's operating areas. It is not necessary for the points to fall in the same operating area.
6. The start and the end times and dates of the traveller's trip request should belong to the operation periods of the service. This means that the provided start time and end time should belong to operation periods of the service, but not necessarily to the same period. Such a trip can be performed in a non-continuous way.

The Matchmaker was implemented using the C++ programming language in the QtCreator IDE, and its source code was documented using Doxygen.

Technical challenges

During the design phase of the Matchmaking Module, we faced the problem of handing a transportation service as digital object. For this reason, we needed a definition of what a transportation service is in order to match it with appropriate internal data structures. Unfortunately, to the best of our knowledge, there is no formal definition of a transportation service as a digital object in the relevant literature, and therefore we have defined the MyCorridor Service Data Model. This data model contains all the necessary information of accurately representing a transportation service in a digital platform. Another technical difficulty we encountered during the operation of the Matchmaking Module was the high computational load. During the operation of the Matchmaking Module, several data structures are produced for multiple travellers at the same time, while several rule checks had to be performed concurrently. In order to efficiently handle these multiple trip requests, we added a parallelization layer to the Matchmaker's source code using directives from the OpenMP [25] shared-memory multiprocessing programming interface. This approach let us efficiently manage

hundreds of requests with response time less than 20 seconds per request, which can be considered as quite low time given all the different combinations trips and services that may arise for a specific trip request.

Experimental Evaluation and Results

In order to evaluate the functionalities of the MyCorridor MaaS app and platform in general and these of the Matchmaking Module in particular, an experimental evaluation framework has been designed and implemented on the project's pilot sites namely Austria, Czech Republic, Netherlands, Italy and Greece. This framework consists of two phases. In the first phase, the MyCorridor app was tested in a protected (lab) environment by users selected based on specific characteristics (e.g. age, gender, education level, etc.). The acceptance of the app by this type of users was recorded using questionnaires answered by the users. The second phase of the experimental framework consists of testing the app on the real world by real users. At the time of writing this document, the second phase of the experimental framework is still in progress, and therefore some results of the first phase are documented in this section. More detailed information of these results can be found in the public deliverable D6.2 of the MyCorridor project [27].

Demographics and background information

This subsection provides an overview of the demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the participants to the first phase on the evaluation on country level and across all countries, respectively. Regarding the gender, we found that Austria, Greece and Italy have a balanced gender ratio, whereas the Czech Republic and the Netherlands had a much higher proportion of male. Overall, 60% of all participants were male, compared to 40% of female participants. Regarding the educational attainment of the respondents, we found that among all respondents, 73% had a higher education, 23% had a secondary education and 4% were classified as other education. Then, regarding the living situation of the respondents, we found that across all countries the majority of respondents (44%) live with a spouse or partner, 27% with family or friend and 28% in single households. Finally, we found that computer literacy of the participants was at a high level for 99% of the respondents.

Results

At the end of the first phase of the evaluation process, several interesting results were recorded. For example, 33% of the questionnaires' respondents answered usability is what they like best about MyCorridor app, followed by the fact that the app is simple and fast (28%) and that they like the idea of MaaS (24%). Additionally, 64% of respondents from all countries said that they could rely on the information they get on MyCorridor app. Since a main type of information the users receive on MyCorridor app is the trips generated by the Matchmaking Module, we interpreted this result as the users' acceptance rate of its functionality. Moreover, 59% of the users (at an aggregated level) said that MyCorridor app was easy to use on their first visit. Finally, based on the respondents' answers from all pilot sites, 75% of them would recommend MyCorridor to a friend.

Conclusions

In this paper, the Matchmaking Module of the MyCorridor MaaS platform was presented. First, the main matchmaking scenarios defined in the context of MyCorridor project were described. Then, the key components of the module along with the technical difficulties we encountered during its implementation were presented. Finally, some preliminary results of the module's evaluation process were provided. A module like the one presented in this work lies in the heart of each real-world MaaS application, and its seamless operation is critical for the successful provision of MaaS offerings to the travellers. This work is not only applicable to the MyCorridor platform, but also for future research and commercial activities concerning the concept of MaaS both in Europe and worldwide.

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